

Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer

Monitoring the world around us since 1864

MUNRO

R W Munro Limited

Monitoring the World Around us Since 1864

The Founder Robert William Munro, F.R.Met.Soc. 1839-1912

Established in 1864, R W Munro has become synonymous with meteorological and hydrological equipment sales and service. Since production of the first Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer in 1892, R W Munro has achieved a reputation for excellence in providing instruments and systems of the highest quality to measure, monitor and record environmental phenomena. Today, Munro products extend right across the technological spectrum. Combining the traditional reliability of Munro craftsmanship with the benefits of the latest electronics enables Munro to supply standard and specialist equipment to meteorological offices, water authorities and government departments world-wide.

Wind Speed & Direction

Mechanical operation - no power supply required

Reliable data on wind speed and wind direction is frequently required in remote locations, where no external power supply is available. Munro supply these self-contained systems for recording continuously, over daily or weekly periods. Operation is entirely mechanical, with spring wound clocks providing the power source for driving the chart drums.

The Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer is universally recognised as the most reliable and accurate instrument of its kind and has been adopted as standard by the British Meteorological Office and by meteorological stations world-wide.

A separate catalogue covers the full range of other Munro equipment for Wind Speed and Direction.

Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer

Wind Speed & Direction

Mechanical operation - no power supply required

Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer IM100

Consisting essentially of a Head Assembly, a Velocity Recorder and a Direction Recorder, the IM100 records wind speed and wind direction simultaneously on a single chart. An important feature of the Dines, is that it records not only average wind velocity over a given time, but also variations in wind force, with the strength and frequency of gusts, providing valuable data on the internal structure of the wind.

The Recorder section includes the sealed cylindrical tank, which is partially filled with water, in which the specially designed float is suspended and a twin pen recording instrument mounted on the top plate of the tank. With every upward or downward movement of the float, corresponding to an increase or decrease in wind force, the pen attached to the top of the float leaves a trace on the upper portion of the chart, so continuously recording velocity. The twin pens of the direction recorder operate separately to provide an uninterrupted record of the wind direction on the lower portion of the same chart. Spring wound clocks and charts for daily or weekly rotation are available.

The Head Assembly, normally mounted 10 metres above the ground, on a mast or tower with the recorder located directly below it, comprises of a balanced vane, which ensures that the wind blows into the open end of a horizontal pitot tube, creating a pressure, while a second vertical static tube is perforated so that air travelling past creates suction. Two separate tubes lead from the Head Assembly to a sealed tank, where acting as a sensitive manometer, differential pressure causes operation of the Velocity Recorder. Variation in wind direction is transmitted by a combination of rods to the twin pen recorder mounted on the top plate of the sealed tank.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	IM100
Speed Range	0 to 110 mph or equivalent
Direction Range	0° to 360°
Speed Scale	0 to 110 mph = 168 mm
Direction Scale	0° to 360° = 45.7 mm
Chart Drive	Hand Wound Clockwork
Clock Accuracy	± 5 minutes per day
Time Scale	0.6" (15.24 mm) = 1 hour (daily chart)
Accuracy	± 2 mph and ± 1°
Resolution	2 mph and 10°
Dimensions	
(Tank & Recorder)	1075 mm (H) 665 mm (W) 390 mm (D)
(Head & Vane)	905 mm (H) Axis to Fin Tip : 825 mm Axis to Balance Weight : 330 mm
Overall Weight	59 kg

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